

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Acetophenone Semicarbazone and *p*-Methoxyacetophenone Semicarbazone by Peroxodisulphate

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Kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone semicarbazone and *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone by peroxodisulphate have been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium. The reaction exhibits a first order dependence with respect to [PDS]. A plot of k^{-1} vs [substrate] is linear. Effects of added H^+ and salt have also been investigated. The stoichiometry is 1:1. A suitable mechanism has been proposed to account for these observations. The large negative ΔS^\ddagger values indicate that the activated complexes are addition complexes of the substrate and PDS. The substituent effect on the reaction rate has been studied. A sharp comparison is made with the corresponding reactions of the similar peroxide SO_5 .

Many valuable natural products with carbonyl groups are crystallised out only in the form of oximes and semicarbazones from their biological sources¹. Since the liberation of parent ketones from these compounds by oxidative hydrolysis is to be achieved in maximum yields, much attention is focussed on the study of such reactions brought about by various reagents. Peroxodisulphate is one such reagent which is found to react with oximes and semicarbazones at measurable rates with quantitative conversion. So far, the kinetics of oxidation of semicarbazones by peroxo compounds have not been reported at all. Hence, in the present paper we report the kinetics of oxidation of acetophenone semicarbazone by peroxodisulphate (PDS).

Results and Discussion

Order with respect to PDS : The concentration of PDS was varied in the range $6.0-10.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} for acetophenone semicarbazone and in the range $1.0-5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} for *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone. The fact that the plots of log [PDS] vs time

were straight lines even beyond 70% completion of the reaction, indicates that the reaction is first order in PDS. Further the pseudo-first order rate constants were found to remain constant at different [PDS] confirming the order with respect to PDS to be unity.

Order with respect to substrate : The plots of log [PDS] vs time (min) at different initial concentrations of the substrate but at a fixed concentration of PDS were linear and the values of k' (s^{-1}) evaluated from the slopes were found to be dependent on the initial concentrations of the substrate. The values of k (s^{-1}) plotted against [substrate] gave a straight line passing through the origin, showing a first order dependence with respect to [substrate] as well as the absence of self-decomposition of PDS (Fig. 1). From the slopes of the above plots the second order rate constants k_2 ($dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$) were evaluated.

Effect of $[H^+]$ and ionic strength : The variation of $[H^+]$ at constant [substrate], [oxidant] and ionic strength was found not to affect the rate of the reaction. Similarly, the influence of

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k' ($\times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$) FOR THE OXIDATION OF ACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE BY PDS

$\times 10^3 [\text{PDS}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^2 [\text{S}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$[\text{H}^+]$ mol dm ⁻³	μ mol dm ⁻³	HOAc %(v/v)	Temp.(°C)			
					50	60	70	80
6.00	10.00	0.4	0.5	30	—	2.11	—	—
7.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	30	—	2.11	—	—
8.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	30	1.62	2.11	3.02	3.43
9.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	30	1.85	2.11	3.11	3.48
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	30	1.58	2.09	3.02	3.62
10.00	6.00	0.4	0.51	30	—	1.20	—	—
10.00	8.00	0.4	0.51	30	1.18	1.66	2.46	2.76
10.00	12.00	0.4	0.51	30	1.79	2.61	3.71	4.12
10.00	14.00	0.4	0.51	30	—	3.03	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.1	0.51	30	—	2.06	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.2	0.51	30	—	2.08	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.3	0.51	30	—	2.07	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.61	30	—	2.07	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.71	30	—	2.08	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.81	30	—	2.06	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	20	—	2.52	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	40	—	1.69	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	50	—	1.24	—	—
10.00	10.00	0.4	0.51	60	—	0.854	—	—

ionic strength by added sodium perchlorate on the reaction rate was found to be negligible indicating² that the reaction occurring is between a neutral species namely the semicarbazone molecule and the negative ion $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$, the active species of the oxidant under the experimental conditions.

Effect of dielectric constant : The general

EVALUATION OF k_2

Fig. 1. (A) Acetophenone semicarbazone at 60° and (B) *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone at 50°

trend observed in the reaction between acetophenone semicarbazone and PDS, the decrease of the rate of the reaction with decrease in the dielectric constant reveals² that there is a charge development in the transition state involving a more polar activated complex than the reactants, a neutral molecule (semicarbazone) and a negative ion $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. This effect on the reaction between *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone and PDS could not be studied due to poor solubility (Tables 1 and 2).

Test for free radical intermediates : The reactions studied exhibited a total second order dependence, first order each in [PDS] and [substrate] whereas for most of the radical reactions the orders with respect to the reactants are often non-integral. Moreover no polymer formation was observed when a freshly distilled acrylonitrile monomer was added to the de-aerated reaction mixture indicating the absence of free radical intermediates.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : A known excess of PDS was allowed to react with a known [substrate] in 30% acetic acid medium.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF k' ($\times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$) FOR THE OXIDATION OF *p*-METHOXYACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE BY PDS

$\times 10^3$ [PDS] mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^2$ [S] mol dm ⁻³	[H ⁺] mol dm ⁻³	μ mol dm ⁻³	HOAc %(v/v)	Temp.(°C)			
					40	50	60	70
1.00	5.00	0.4	0.51	80	—	2.19	—	—
2.00	5.00	0.4	0.51	80	—	2.19	—	—
3.00	5.00	0.4	0.51	80	1.39	2.11	3.77	6.14
4.00	5.00	0.4	0.51	80	1.40	2.22	3.80	6.15
5.00	5.00	0.4	0.51	80	1.39	2.24	3.89	6.14
5.00	6.00	0.4	0.51	80	1.66	2.66	4.67	7.36
5.00	7.00	0.4	0.51	80	1.92	3.20	5.22	8.68
5.00	8.00	0.4	0.51	80	—	3.70	—	—
5.00	9.00	0.4	0.51	80	—	4.13	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.5	0.51	80	—	2.23	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.6	0.51	80	—	2.25	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.7	0.51	80	—	2.26	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.8	0.51	80	—	2.24	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.4	0.61	80	—	2.24	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.4	0.71	80	—	2.26	—	—
5.00	5.00	0.4	0.81	80	—	2.25	—	—

The stoichiometry of the reactions were found to be 1 : 1. These reaction mixtures were extracted with ether; the ether layers were concentrated and used for product analysis. One drop of the test solution was warmed with seven drops of 0.2% aqueous azobenzene phenylhydrazone in sulphuric acid and four drops of concentrated sulphuric acid and cooled. Then a few drops of alcohol and enough chloroform were added to form a lower layer, followed by three drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The chloroform layer became coloured on shaking, indicating the presence of the parent ketone³. This product was further confirmed by tlc experiments.

Rate and activation parameters : From the observed kinetics the rate law for the disappearance of PDS is given as

$$-\frac{d[\text{PDS}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{PDS}][\text{substrate}] \quad (1)$$

E_a , ΔH^\ddagger , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are calculated as $51.9 \pm 1.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, 31.2 kJ mol^{-1} , $-70.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and 36.7 kJ mol^{-1} respectively, for the oxidation reaction of acetophenone semicarbazone by PDS. Similarly for *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone these values are $42 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, 39.5 kJ mol^{-1} , $-48.5 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and 55.7 kJ mol^{-1} respectively.

Mechanism : Peroxo compounds generally react with compounds containing $>\text{C}=\text{N}-$ by the nucleophilic attack of oxygen of the peroxo-linkage on the carbon atom to form the corresponding oxaziranes⁴. Oxaziranes then hydrolyse to give the corresponding ketones⁵. In the light of the experimental results a suitable mechanism has been proposed which is presented in Scheme 1.

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE OXIDATION HYDROLYSES OF ACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE AND *p*-METHOXYACETOPHENONE SEMICARBAZONE

Temp.(°C)	Acetophenone semicarbazone			<i>p</i> -Methoxyacetophenonesemicarbazone			
	50°	60°	70°	40°	50°	60°	70°
$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$ (for PMS)	2.15	3.65	6.50	4.95	10.9	19.7	34.3
$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$ (for PDS)	1.98	2.31	3.12	2.65	4.84	7.10	12.7

Scheme 1

Comparison of PDS with PMS : The oxidative hydrolyses of acetophenone semicarbazone and *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone by peroxomonosulphate (PMS) have been studied⁶. The reactions are found to follow a similar mechanism as that of PDS. The second order rate constants at different temperatures for all these reactions are given in Table 3. From these values it is inferred that PMS is a better oxidant than PDS in effecting the oxidation of acetophenone semicarbazone and *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone, even though the oxidation potential for PDS ($E^{\circ} = 2.01 \text{ V}$)⁷ is higher than that of PMS ($E^{\circ} = 1.82 \text{ V}$)⁸. A similar trend has been observed in the oxidation of a number of other substrates like halide ions⁹ and aliphatic¹⁰ and aromatic aldehydes¹¹.

Structure and reactivity : The rate constants for *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone could not be determined in 30% (v/v) acetic acid medium due to lack of solubility of the substrate. The rate constants for acetophenone semicarbazone could not be measured in 80% (v/v) acetic acid medium as the rate became too slow to be measured. Hence a graph was drawn between the rate constant of acetophenone semicarbazone and

the percentage of acetic acid. It was extrapolated and the value in 80% (v/v) acetic acid was determined. This value was found to be $0.10 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Under the conditions, the rate constant for *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone was found to be $3.81 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Thus the reactivity trend is found to be *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone > acetophenone semicarbazone. In general, the +*M* effect of the *p*-methoxy substituent reduces the electron deficiency at the carbon atom of the reaction site thus retarding the nucleophilic attack at the double bonded carbon¹². On the contrary, in the present investigation, the increase in the electron density on the double bonded carbon due to the +*M* effect of *p*-methoxy group favours greater polarisation of the C-N bond. This facilitates the nucleophilic attack of PDS as shown in Scheme 2. Thus the enhancement of the rate of the reaction by *p*-methoxy substituent substantiates the fact that the reaction proceeds via the formation of oxazirane intermediate.

Scheme 2

Experimental

A 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solution of peroxodisulphate was prepared in double distilled water and its strength determined by iodometric method. Acetophenone semicarbazone and *p*-methoxyacetophenone semicarbazone were prepared from the respective ketones by the usual procedure¹³ and their melting points were checked with literature values. Acetic acid used as the solvent in the kinetic studies was purified by the standard procedure¹⁴. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

The kinetic runs were carried out in 30%

aqueous acid medium in the temperature range 40–80°, keeping the concentration of the substrate in considerable excess over that of PDS. The pseudo-first order rate was followed by the disappearance of PDS using iodometric method. The rate constants (k') were found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

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References

1. P. S. KALSI, "Chemistry of Natural Products", Kalyani, New Delhi, 1983, p. 262.
2. K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", Tata-McGraw Hill, New Delhi, 1965, p. 229.
3. F. FRITZ, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1960, p. 228.
4. W. D. EMMONS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6208.
5. V. MADAN and L. B. CLAPP, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6078.
6. T. S. JANI BAI, Ph.D. Thesis, Bharathidasan University, 1988.
7. W. M. LATIMER, "The Oxidation States of the Elements and their Potentials in Aqueous Solutions", Prentice-Hall, New Jersey, 1956, p. 78.
8. W. V. STEELA and E. H. APPELMAN, *J. Chem. Thermodyn.*, 1982, **14**, 337.
9. D. H. FORTNUM, C. J. BATTAGLIA, S. R. COHEN and J. O. EDWARDS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 778.
10. R. RENGANATHAN and P. MARUTHAMUTHU, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1986, 285.
11. R. RENGANATHAN and P. MARUTHAMUTHU, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1986, **18**, 49.
12. J. MARCH, "Advanced Organic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1987, p. 782.
13. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Pactical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1968, p. 344.
14. K. J. P. ORTAN and A. E. BRADFIELD, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 983.

